

Application of PM Tubular Linear Motor Drive as the Electromechanical Linear Actuator of a 6 DOF Parallel Manipulator

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Abstract — This paper describes the study of Permanent Magnet Tubular Linear Synchronous Motor (PM-TLSM) as the electromechanical linear actuator of a Six Degree of Freedom (6 DOF) Parallel Manipulator. The dynamic models of the PM-TLSM and the position drive controller are derived and implemented in Matlab in order to obtain simulation results to evaluate the dynamic response. The experimental results of the electromechanical linear positioning drive are presented and discussed to validate the mathematical model.

represents the rotation moves according to the axes X, Y, Z, respectively.

Fig.2 presents two topologies of 6 DOF parallel manipulators. It depicts hydraulic motors as linear actuators of the parallel manipulator and Fig.2(b) presents electromechanical drive actuators with rotary to linear conversion.

1. Introduction

The 6 DOF parallel manipulators are widely used in flight simulators, and are often designed to emulate the aeronautic and other vehicle motions.

Considering a three-dimension system coordinates given by directions X, Y, and Z, the 6 DOF movements can be represented as shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1. Six degrees of freedom representation;
(a) translation moves; (b) rotary moves.

In Fig.1(a), the labels surge, sway and heave, represents the translation moves according to the axes X, Y, Z, respectively. In Fig.1(b), the labels roll, pitch and yaw,

Fig.2. 6-DOF parallel manipulators; (a) hydraulics actuators, [1];
(b) mechanical drive.

A. Forces applied to the linear actuators in the 6DOF parallel manipulator

Fig.3 to Fig.8 shows the simulations results obtained with the 6 DOF parallel manipulator simulation software MD Nastran™ developed by MSC.Software®, in steady-state conditions, for all 6 DOF extreme positions, with 2000N load force on the top platform of the parallel manipulator. This simulation software uses all the physic characteristics of the parallel manipulator elements. All the elements are projected in CAD environment and imported to MD Nastran™. As it can be seen in Fig.3 to Fig.8, the linear actuators have to withstand large variations of the load force according to the top platform position.

Fig.3. Initial position of the parallel manipulator.

Fig.4. Surge translation by $-0,27$ m .

Fig.5. Sway translation by $-0,24$ m .

Fig.6. Yaw rotation by $0,56$ rad .

Fig.7. Roll rotation by $-0,44$ rad .

Fig.8. Pitch rotation by $-0,42$ rad .

Table I resumes the simulation results for minimum and maximum forces of the linear actuators obtained in 6 DOF extreme positions.

TABLE I
FORCES APPLIED TO THE LINEAR ACTUATORS

6 DOF moves	Value	Minimum Force (N)	Maximum Force (N)
Roll	0,44rad	83	738
Pitch	-0,42rad	106	749
Yaw	0,56rad	126	642
Surge	-0,27m	83	763
Sway	-0,24m	0	719
Heave	0m	410	

B. Electromechanical linear actuators

In order to replace the hydraulic and pneumatic linear actuators, which are generally heavy and voluminous, due to other support equipments, the electromechanical linear actuators can be an advantageous solution. In this field, two major options using electric machines are available in industry: 1) electromechanical linear actuators with mechanical rotary to linear conversion and 2) linear electric motors.

The Fig.9 shows a cutaway view of an electromechanical linear actuator where the main parts are described, [2].

Fig.9. A cutaway view of an electromechanical linear actuator.

The Fig.10 illustrates the permanent magnet tubular linear synchronous motor (PM-TLSM) considered in this paper,

the CLD4206D model from California Linear Devices, Inc, showing the shaft containing rings rare-earth neodymium-iron-boron magnets with radial magnetization, [3].

Fig.10. A cutaway view of PM-TLSM.

Table II presents a comparison between the linear actuators used for heavy loads, [4].

TABLE II
COMPARATIVE TABLE OF LINEAR ACTUATORS FOR HEAVY LOADS

Characteristics	Tubular motors	Mechanical drives	Hydraulics
Speed ($\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)	2,5	0,25	0,25
Accuracy (mm)	0,025	0,025	0,25
Stiffness	High	Medium	Medium
Friction	Medium	Medium	High
Temperature	125°C	125°C	50°C
Shock loading	High	Medium	High
Efficiency (%)	50	40	25
Noise (dB)	40	80	120
Environmental concerns	None	Minimal	Oil leaks and disposal
Controllability	Fully programmable (no backlash)	Fixed move profiles (cams), Backlash (ballscrews)	Limited move profiles
Maintenance	Reduce	Medium	High

The linear motor applies force directly to the load, and does not require any intermediate mechanism to convert rotary motion into linear motion. Also they can offer significant advantages over conventional linear motion systems, such as hydraulic linear actuators, motors drives by cams, ballscrews and belts, in terms of efficiency, low cost maintenance, no power loss in rotary-linear conversion, motor/generator operation, speed and force control and positional accuracy.

2. Electromechanical Linear position drive model

Figure 11 presents the global scheme of electromechanical linear position drive. The PM-TLSM is driven by a position controller using power converters and a linear encoder as feedback device. The linear incremental digital encoder is the position sensor that measures the real time displacement and the variation of motion.

The mathematical dynamic models of the PM-TLSM and the position drive controller are derived and implemented in Matlab in order to obtain simulation results to evaluate the dynamic response.

A. PM Tubular Linear Motor model

In order to simplify the PM-TLSM model, the following assumptions are considered, [5]:

- windings inductances are constant in any shaft position;
- shaft length is considered infinite, so the end effects are neglected;
- magnetic circuit model do not includes magnetic saturation;
- permeability of the iron is infinite, so the iron losses are neglected;
- flux density reaction produced by stator current is neglected when compared with the PM flux density.

Fig.11. Global scheme of electromechanical linear position drive.

Based on Faraday's law, the equations that describes the electric part of the PM-TLSM are given in (1).

$$\begin{cases} u_{an} = R_s \cdot i_a + \frac{d\Psi_a}{dt} \\ u_{bn} = R_s \cdot i_b + \frac{d\Psi_b}{dt} \\ u_{cn} = R_s \cdot i_c + \frac{d\Psi_c}{dt} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In (1) u_{an} , u_{bn} , u_{cn} are the single phase supply voltages, i_a , i_b , i_c are the stator windings currents, R_s is the related resistance for each phase and Ψ_a , Ψ_b , Ψ_c represent the linkage fluxes on a , b , c phases, respectively, (2).

$$\begin{cases} \Psi_a = L_s i_a + M_s (i_b + i_c) + \Psi_m \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{\tau_p} x\right) \\ \Psi_b = L_s \cdot i_b + M_s (i_a + i_c) + \Psi_m \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{\tau_p} x - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\ \Psi_c = L_s \cdot i_c + M_s (i_a + i_b) + \Psi_m \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{\tau_p} x + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In (2) L_s and M_s are the stator self-induction and the mutual induction coefficients per phase, respectively. The linkage fluxes Ψ_a , Ψ_b , Ψ_c on three phases windings have a component with co-sinusoidal variation, whose maximum value is the flux established by permanent magnets, Ψ_m .

The tubular linear motor model can be written in a compacted form (3).

$$\mathbf{u}_{abc} = \mathbf{R}_s \cdot \mathbf{i}_{abc} + \mathbf{L}_{abc} \cdot \frac{d\mathbf{i}_{abc}}{dt} + \frac{dx}{dt} \cdot \frac{d\mathbf{\Psi}_{abc}}{dx} \quad (3)$$

In (3) \mathbf{u}_{abc} is the vector voltage applied to the tubular linear motor; \mathbf{R}_s is the resistance matrix of the stator windings; \mathbf{i}_{abc} is the stator windings current matrix; \mathbf{L}_{abc} is the self-induction and mutual induction coefficients matrix; $\frac{d\mathbf{\Psi}_{abc}}{dx}$, represents the derivative of linkage fluxes matrix established by permanent magnets in stator windings; $\frac{dx}{dt}$ is the synchronous linear speed, v , which is related with supply frequency and pole pitch, (4), [6].

$$v = \frac{dx}{dt} = 2f\tau_p \quad (4)$$

The electromagnetic force, F_e , can be obtained from magnetic coenergy derivative, W_{cm} , in order to the position coordinate, (5), [7].

$$F_e = \frac{\partial W_{cm}}{\partial x} = [\mathbf{i}_{abc}]^T \frac{d}{dx} [\mathbf{\Psi}_{abc}] \quad (5)$$

Considering that the PM-TLSM is placed on vertical position, the mechanical equation is given by the second Newton's law, (6).

$$F_e = m_T \left(\frac{dv}{dt} + g \right) + f(v) \quad (6)$$

In (6), m_T represents the inertia of the linear shaft and load mass in kilogram and g is the gravitational acceleration. The resistant force, $f(v)$, can be translated by (7).

$$f(v) = K_v v + F_c \operatorname{sgn}(v) + (F_s - F_c) e^{-\left(\frac{v}{v_s}\right)^2} \operatorname{sgn}(v) \quad (7)$$

In (7), K_v represents the viscous attrition coefficient; F_c and F_s are the Coulomb and the static forces, respectively; v_s represents the Stribeck effect and $\operatorname{sgn}(v)$ represents a speed signal function, [8].

The equations (3), (5), (6) and (7) characterize the PM-TLSM model in abc coordinates.

B. Vectorial current controller

Figure 12 presents the vectorial current controller (VCC) that regulates the stator winding currents in $\alpha\beta$ reference frame, within the small band around reference currents. The motor currents are compared with the reference currents and the switching commands, γ_a , γ_b and γ_c , are generated by the voltage vector selection table, [9].

Fig.12. Block diagram of the vectorial current controller.

From de equation (3), the output of three-phase inverter can be expressed in $\alpha\beta$ reference frame by (8).

$$\mathbf{L}_{\alpha\beta} \frac{d\mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta}}{dt} = \mathbf{u}_{\alpha\beta} - \mathbf{R}_s \mathbf{i}_{\alpha\beta} - \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{d\mathbf{\Psi}_{\alpha\beta}}{dx} \quad (8)$$

Using the three-phase inverter output voltages, the VCC controls the output currents to obtain stator currents with a sinusoidal shape feature and to react to the cascade controllers actions. The VCC uses two hysteretic comparators to evaluate the current errors in three discrete values: negative, null and positive. This control strategy is followed by using three level comparators, which are obtained by the sum of the output of two comparators with two different hysteretic levels, large (δ_{La} , $\delta_{L\beta}$) and narrow (δ_{Na} , $\delta_{N\beta}$). The outputs current errors and the commutation frequency of the semiconductor devices are dependent of the hysteretic comparator window size. Reduced hysteretic leads to reduce errors in control currents, but increases the commutation frequency of the semiconductor devices, [9].

position drive. The Fig. 15 and 16 presents the experimental results for 130N and 740N load forces tests. The vertical gain for position error is 50mm/div, for acceleration command, a^* , is 10ms⁻²/div, and for stator currents is 3A/div in Fig.15 and 7,5A/div in Fig.16.

Fig.15. Experimental results with a 130N load force.

Fig.16. Experimental results with a 740N load force.

The relative error of the comparison between experimental and simulation results to 130N load force, is lower than 5% in position error. For the stator currents this relative error is lower than 15% in acceleration and deceleration periods and lower than 10% in constant speed period.

Analyzing the experimental results to 740N load force and comparing with simulations, the relative error is lower than 7% for position error. The relative error for stator currents is lower than 15%.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, a comparative analysis of the linear actuators to drive the 6 DOF parallel manipulators is presented. Special focus is made on PM-TLSM as the electromechanical linear actuator.

A mathematical dynamic model of electromechanical linear position drive is presented and discussed.

The comparison between the simulation results and the experimental tests validates the dynamic model of the electromechanical linear position drive.

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